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AN EMPRICAL STUDY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION WITH REFRENCE TO HYUNDAI CARS

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ABSTRACT

Every dimension of market orientation emphasis the ability of intermediaries in order to continuously sense and act on the events and trends in present and prospective markets. Today's highly sophisticated life makes the marketer to know the pulse of the market. If companies want to survive in the competitive market they have to identify the needs of the customer and try to fulfill them. The economy is referred to as "CUSTOMER DRIVEN" With firms allowing to customers to dictate specifications and quality standards and also working out corporate strategies evolve around the consumer. Consumer behavior is not predictable. Consumer needs are dynamic; therefore, he/she is always looking for something new to satisfy new needs. This is the reason why the consumer satisfaction has emerged as a separate research area of study since, the past few decades. The study has been undertaken to determine CONSUMER SATISFACTION the research has been taken up in analysis of CONSUMER SATISFACTION with reference to "HYUNDAI CARS" in a customer driven, need based market

Keywords: *Consumer Satisfaction, Customer Driven, Hyundai Cars*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Marketing can be defined as "the activity, set of institutions, and processes for creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging offerings that have value for customers, clients, partners, and society at large." It is total system of interacting business activities assigned to plan, price, promote and distribute, wants satisfying products and services to existing and potential customers.

The marketing concept is, market focused and customers oriented coordinated marketing effort aimed at generating customer satisfaction, which in turn is a key to achieve the organizational goals. The concept of consumer satisfaction occupies pivotal position in marketing thought and practice. Satisfaction is the major outcome of the marketing activity and services to link process and culminating in purchase and consumption with the help of past purchase phenomenon such as changes in attitude, repeat purchase and brand loyalty.

2.0 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Customer satisfaction is the common word used by the business people for the success of organization in the today world. Due to increasing heavy competition in every product –line it becomes difficult for the companies to retain the customers for longer time. To retain the customer for longer time the marketer has to do only one thing i.e. customer satisfaction . If the customer is fully satisfied by the product it will not only lead to success of the organization but also will bring many benefits for the company. The customers will be less process sensitive and they will remain for a longer period and buy addition products overtimes as the company introduce related products or improved, so customer satisfaction is gaining high importance in the present days. Every company is conducting survey on customer satisfaction level on their products to make the products up to the satisfaction level of customers.

3.0 RESEARCH METHDOLOGY

3.1 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Scope covers only Hyundai car owners. Their preferences are on basis of various factors and consumer satisfaction level is on basis of future purchase and comparison with other brands. The survey is conducted in Hyderabad. The sample survey is taken for a number of “100”HYUNDAI customers

3.2 HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

In this study there are two main hypotheses according to two main factors of occupation and income, which can divide into some sub-hypothesis as follow:

1) H0: There is no difference in satisfaction level of customers with different occupation.

H1: There is difference in satisfaction level of customers with different occupation.

It can be measured through the following sub-hypothesis:

1.a) H0: There is no significant association between occupation and the reason to purchase Hyundai cars.

H1: There is significant association between occupation and the reason to purchase Hyundai cars.

1.b) H0: There is no significant association between occupation and parameters considered to purchase Hyundai cars.

H1: There is significant association between occupation and parameters considered to purchase Hyundai cars.

1.c) H0: There is no significant association between occupation and price of Hyundai cars.

H1: There is significant association between occupation and price of Hyundai cars.

1.d) H0: There is no significant association between occupation and performance of Hyundai cars.

H1: There is significant association between occupation and performance of Hyundai cars.

2) H0: There is no difference in satisfaction level of customers with different income.

H1: There is difference in satisfaction level of customers with different income.

Sub-Hypotheses to be considered are:

2.a) H0: There is no significant association between income and the reasons to purchase Hyundai cars.

H1: There is significant association between income and the reasons to purchase Hyundai cars.

2.b) H0: There is no significant association between income and sources of awareness of Hyundai cars.

H1: There is significant association between income and sources of awareness of Hyundai cars.

2.c) H0: There is no significant association between income and parameters considered to purchase Hyundai cars.

H1: There is significant association between income and parameters considered to purchase Hyundai cars.

2.d) H0: There is no significant association between income and the price of Hyundai cars.

H1: There is significant association between income and the price of Hyundai cars.

3.3 TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES

- a. Percentages
- b. Bar and Pie Diagrams
- c. chi square

3.4 SAMPLING METHODOLOGY

a) Sampling Technique

The technique applied in this project is “Simple random method”

b) Sampling Size

100 customers are taken as the samples for the study.

3.5 DATA SOURCES

a) Primary Data

The data is collected through holding discussions with the employees of the company and discussing the questionnaires with existing customers of the company.

b) Secondary Data

Secondary data has been collected from various sources like text books, journals, articles, published documents, annual reports, magazines and websites.

4.0 ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

DATA ANALYSIS

Occupation * reason for purchase

Table No: 4.1- Analysis of the relationship between occupation and the reasons to purchase Hyundai cars

		reason for purchase				Total	
		Looks of the vehicle	Cost of the vehicle	Availability of services	Manufacture reputation		
Occupation	Retired	Count	0	4	0	1	5
		% within occupation	.0%	80.0%	.0%	20.0%	100.0%
	House Wife	Count	0	2	6	0	8
		% within occupation	.0%	25.0%	75.0%	.0%	100.0%
	Business	Count	0	1	1	5	7
		% within occupation	.0%	14.3%	14.3%	71.4%	100.0%
	Professionals	Count	6	5	12	7	30
		% within occupation	20.0%	16.7%	40.0%	23.3%	100.0%
	Government Employee	Count	4	8	21	17	50
		% within occupation	8.0%	16.0%	42.0%	34.0%	100.0%
Total		Count	10	20	40	30	100
		% within occupation	10.0%	20.0%	40.0%	30.0%	100.0%

H0: There is no significant association between occupation and reason for purchase Hyundai cars.

Table No: 4.2-Chi-Square Tests of occupation * the reasons for purchase Hyundai cars

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	27.921 ^a	12	.006
Likelihood Ratio	28.584	12	.005
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.053	1	.305
N of Valid Cases	100		

a. 13 cells (65.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .50.

From the above table it is clear that chi square sig. value is 0.006 (less than 0.05). So the null hypothesis is rejected. Finally it is concluded that there is significant association between occupation and reason for purchase Hyundai cars.

Occupation * parameters considered

HO: There is no significant association between occupation and parameters considered to purchased Hyundai cars

Table No: 4.3- Analysis of the relationship between occupation and the parameters considered to purchase Hyundai cars

			parameters considered						
			Accessories	Pickup	Engine capacity	colour	price	Looks	Total
Occupation	Retired	Count	1	1	0	0	3	0	5
		% within occupation	20.0%	20.0%	.0%	.0%	60.0%	.0%	100.0%
	House Wife	Count	0	2	0	0	5	1	8
		% within occupation	.0%	25.0%	.0%	.0%	62.5%	12.5%	100.0%
	Business	Count	0	4	0	0	2	1	7
		% within occupation	.0%	57.1%	.0%	.0%	28.6%	14.3%	100.0%
	Professionals	Count	5	9	6	4	4	2	30
		% within occupation	16.7%	30.0%	20.0%	13.3%	13.3%	6.7%	100.0%
	Government Employee	Count	9	14	14	6	1	6	50
		% within occupation	18.0%	28.0%	28.0%	12.0%	2.0%	12.0%	100.0%
Total		Count	15	30	20	10	15	10	100
		% within occupation	15.0%	30.0%	20.0%	10.0%	15.0%	10.0%	100.0%

Table No: 4.4-Chi-Square Tests of occupation * the parameters considered to purchase Hyundai cars

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	39.385 ^a	20	.006
Likelihood Ratio	42.424	20	.002
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.091	1	.024
N of Valid Cases	100		

a. 22 cells (73.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .50.

From the above table it is clear that chi square sig. value is 0.006 (less than 0.05). So the null hypothesis is rejected. Finally it is concluded that there is significant association between occupation and parameters considered in Hyundai cars.

Occupation * price

HO: There is no significant association between occupation and price of Hyundai cars.

5.0 FINDINGS

- In the analysis of customer satisfaction with Hyundai cars, respondents were segmented on the basis of occupation and income according to which they were asked about the sources of awareness, parameter considered, performance, price and the reasons to purchase Hyundai cars.
- Six categories of occupations including retired persons, house wives, business persons, professionals, government employees and others were considered for the study.
- The respondents also were segmented into the five categories as follows:

Up to 3 lakhs, 3-5 lakhs, 5-7 lakhs, 7-10 lakhs and above 10 lakhs income level.

SUGGESTIONS

- From the study the customers prefer more service centers which give the best services.
- From the study the respondents are ready to know about the details. Describing both the advantages and disadvantages of the vehicle is very important. “Customers friendly” attitude is a must for any Business Deal.
- Spare parts should be made available at lower rate.
- Provide High-way horn and reverse horn.
- Improve service and train the service personnel. After sales service is a very important factor in case of automobile sector which may induce buying or stop people from buying the particular brand of vehicle.
- Maintain the same demand in the market.

CONCLUSIONS

- From the findings and analysis it is clear that regardless the occupation and the income level the most considered parameters while purchasing Hyundai cars are pick up with 30% and engine with 20%.
- From the study it shows that 32% of the consumers are highly satisfied of the product performance and sales service, 47% of them are satisfied and the rest 20% are dissatisfied.
- Apart from the customer income or occupation circumstance, the most preferred reasons to purchase Hyundai cars are availability of services with 40% and manufacture reputation with 30%.
- From the analysis it can be concluded that the first important source of awareness about Hyundai cars is friends and relatives with 45%, and the second one is Television ads.
- Apart from income or occupation circumstance majority of the customers believes that the product price is reasonable.
- Since each customer is like an asset for an organization the company should try to improve in the area of dissatisfaction.
- It is clear that getting new customer is double the cost of retaining the old customer so the company should focus on retaining the old customers whom in the future purchase the product or recommend others to purchase the product. Thus they help directly or indirectly for the product sale.

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